

Research on the Impact of e-commerce on International Trade and Countermeasures

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Abstract: This paper aims to explore the impact and countermeasures of e-commerce on international trade. Through research on the relationship between e-commerce and international trade, the impact of e-commerce on international trade, and China's foreign trade e-commerce, we can draw some conclusions. E-commerce plays an important role in promoting the development of international trade. It can promote the development of international trade, reduce the cost of international trade, and promote innovation in international trade. There is an interdependent relationship between e-commerce and international trade, but the application of e-commerce in international trade faces some challenges, such as network security, intellectual property protection, cross-border payment and other issues, which need to be effectively resolved.

Keywords: E-commerce, International Trade, Cross-Border Trade, Trade Policy

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1 Introduction

1.1 Research Background

With the continuous development of Internet technology, e-commerce has become an important part of global economic development. The emergence of e-commerce has greatly changed the traditional business model and has a profound impact on international trade. Therefore, studying the impact and countermeasures of e-commerce on international trade has important practical significance and far-reaching historical significance.

1.2 Research Purpose and Significance

This paper aims to explore the impact and countermeasures of e-commerce on international trade, with a view to providing reference and reference for the development of e-commerce in my country. Specifically, the research purposes of this paper include: analyze the relationship between e-commerce and international trade; explore the impact of e-commerce on international trade; propose countermeasures for e-commerce on international trade.

1.3 Summary of Related Research at Home and Abroad

At present, domestic and foreign scholars have conducted extensive research on the impact and countermeasures of e-commerce on international trade. Foreign scholars have conducted in-depth discussions mainly from the development history of e-commerce, the

characteristics of e-commerce, and the advantages of e-commerce; while domestic scholars have mainly conducted in-depth discussions from the development status of e-commerce, the development trends of e-commerce, and the policy environment of e-commerce. Research has been carried out in other aspects. This paper will review the current status of related research at home and abroad in order to provide a reference for the research of this paper.

2 Overview of E-Commerce

2.1 Concept, Characteristics, Development

History and Competitive Advantages

E-commerce refers to a business model that uses Internet technology to conduct commercial activities through the Internet. It has the following characteristics: informatization and networking; virtualization of transactions; globalization of transactions; personalization of transactions.

The development process of e-commerce can be divided into three stages: information transmission stage; e-commerce stage; mobile e-commerce stage. The competitive advantages of e-commerce are mainly reflected in the following aspects: reduce transaction costs; improve transaction efficiency; expand market space; improve customer satisfaction.

2.2 The Impact of using E-Commerce on Enterprises

The impact of e-commerce on enterprises is mainly

reflected in the following aspects: expand sales channels; reduce transaction costs; improve transaction efficiency; improve customer satisfaction; improve corporate image; promote corporate innovation; improve corporate competitiveness. The application of e-commerce can enable enterprises to better adapt to market changes and improve their core competitiveness.

3 E-commerce and international Trade

3.1 The Interdependent Relationship Between the Two and the Current Challenges They Face

There is an interdependent relationship between e-commerce and international trade. E-commerce provides a more convenient and efficient transaction method for international trade, and it also brings new opportunities and challenges to the development of international trade. Currently, the application of e-commerce in international trade is facing some challenges, such as network security, intellectual property protection, cross-border payment and other issues, which need to be effectively resolved.

3.2 Impact of E-Commerce on International Trade

The impact of e-commerce on international trade is mainly reflected in the following aspects:

Promote the development of international trade: E-commerce provides a more convenient and efficient transaction method for international trade, which expands the scale of international trade and also brings new opportunities and challenges to the development of international trade.

Reduce international trade costs: The application of e-commerce can reduce the costs of international trade, improve the efficiency of international trade, and also reduce the risks of international trade.

Promote innovation in international trade: The application of e-commerce can promote innovation in international trade, promote the transformation and upgrading of international trade, and improve the competitiveness of international trade.

4 China's Foreign Trade E-Commerce

4.1 The Development Status of China's E-Commerce and its Positioning in Foreign Trade

The development of e-commerce in China has always been in a stage of rapid development. According to data released by the Ministry of Commerce, my country's cross-border e-commerce import and export scale exceeded 2 trillion yuan for the first time in 2022, reaching 2.1 trillion yuan, an increase of 7.1% over 2021, accounting for 4.9% of the total import and export value of national trade in goods¹. The positioning of China's e-commerce in foreign trade is to use e-commerce as a new trade method to promote the transformation and upgrading of trade methods, improve trade efficiency, and promote trade balance.

4.2 Countermeasures for China's use of E-Commerce

China's countermeasures for utilizing e-commerce mainly include the following aspects:

Promote the integration of e-commerce and traditional trade: Through the integration of e-commerce and traditional trade, promote the transformation and upgrading of trade methods, improve trade efficiency, and promote trade balance.

Strengthen the supervision of e-commerce: Strengthen the supervision of e-commerce, establish and improve the credit system of e-commerce, protect the rights and interests of consumers, and maintain market order.

Promote the internationalization of e-commerce: Promote the internationalization of e-commerce, strengthen cooperation with international e-commerce platforms, expand overseas markets, and improve the international competitiveness of my country's e-commerce.

5 Conclusion

This paper aims to explore the impact and countermeasures of e-commerce on international trade. Through research on the relationship between e-commerce and international trade, the impact of e-commerce on international trade, and China's foreign trade e-commerce, we can draw the following conclusions:

E-commerce plays an important role in promoting the development of international trade. It can promote the development of international trade, reduce the cost of international trade, and promote innovation in international trade.

There is an interdependent relationship between e-commerce and international trade, but the application of e-commerce in international trade faces some challenges, such as network security, intellectual property protection, cross-border payment and other issues, which need to be effectively resolved.

The development of China's e-commerce has always been in a stage of rapid development. The positioning of China's e-commerce in foreign trade is to use e-commerce as a new trade method, promote the transformation and

upgrading of trade methods, improve trade efficiency, and promote trade balance. China's strategies for utilizing e-commerce mainly include promoting the integration of e-commerce and traditional trade, strengthening the supervision of e-commerce, and promoting the internationalization of e-commerce.

management of enterprises, institutional construction of technology-based enterprises, and development models of small and micro enterprises.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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